

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: UNITED STATES

Collaborative research as an early career scientist has changed the way I view science

Rosaura J. Chapina
University of Vermont
Burlington, Vermont United States
Email: Rosaura.Chapina@uvm.edu

Climate change has and will continue to affect our oceans, lakes, forests, deserts, the flora and fauna, and people who live in these environments, and has shaped the way we communicate our science. As a first-year Ph.D. student, I aspired to help save the planet. I was convinced that my science would achieve that. Pursuing a Ph.D. is difficult and can often be an isolating journey. However, my journey has been positively influenced by great colleagues and collaborations that have helped to mold my career. When I started my Ph.D., I had a small community. I am now part of various collaborations where I have gained mentors and a wide, diverse community of scientists—people I can reach out to and bounce off ideas.

Fig. 1 Participants at the [GLEON](#) meeting held in Ryn, Poland. (Photo by Jens Nejtgaard)

Being a member of the Global Lake Ecological Observatory Network (GLEON; Fig. 1) has allowed me to discover a new world where ideas emerge, projects develop, and collaborations are formed. Climate change does not have borders; it is a problem our lakes face not only in the U.S., Mexico, or China; it is a global issue. It is here and it is real. Global collaborative projects have challenged the way I think and changed the way I do science. In order to solve the large issues our planet is currently facing; we need interdisciplinary projects led by diverse teams. While as an early career scientist, it is intimidating

Fig. 2 Fecund female *Mysis* (Photo by Chris Liazos)

to be part of conversations and even disagree with renowned scientists, having diverse groups from all career stages allows for innovation and creativity.

There are a few aspects of collaborative science that I believe are crucial for professional development. One crucial skill I was able to gain through collaborative experiences was to actively participate in conversations where disagreement emerges and navigate through conflict resolution to come to a consensus. Communicating to different audiences with different backgrounds and views is another skill that is strengthened by being part of large diverse collaborations. Having to adapt and be flexible when working with people from different cultures and disciplines is vital. By being flexible, you also learn about new perspectives and different ways of brainstorming/designing a project.

My research focuses on understanding the diel vertical migration (DVM) patterns of a mysid shrimp, *Mysis diluviana* (Fig. 2), a large zooplankton that plays a vital role in lake systems by transferring nutrients from benthic to pelagic habitats. *Mysis* serves as a key food source for many pelagic and benthic fishes in north temperate lakes.

At the start of my Ph.D., my research was very local. I was focusing on understanding the migration of *Mysis* in Lake Champlain, Vermont, U.S and Lake Ontario, Canada/U.S. My advisor, Dr. Jason Stockwell (stockwelllaboratory.com), then motivated me to think globally and introduced me to GLEON. I attended a GLEON All Hands' meeting in Huntsville, Ontario, Canada. At that meeting, we were separated into working groups. In these working groups, graduate students, postdocs, and renowned scientists all participate in research discussions and brainstorm ideas for collaborative projects together and pitch ideas as a team. This was very surprising to me. It was eye-opening to see how scientists from different backgrounds and experiences came together to create and discuss potential research projects. I was pleased to be in a room where all viewpoints were valued despite career stages. At that GLEON meeting, I not only participated in research discussions, I ended up leading a global collaborative project. I went from evaluating the migration of one organism in two lakes to leading a global collaborative project that focused on assessing the migration patterns of *Mysis* in nine lakes.

Collaborative research and team science are important skill sets to master but are often purely experiential and unfortunately are not taught or typically encouraged during your Ph.D. In 2020, I was selected to be part of a graduate student fellowship program called Lake Expedition 2020 (fellowship.gleon.org). This fellowship trains nine graduate students from different disciplines and institutions across the globe (Fig. 3). All activities were supported, in part, by funding through the U.S National Science Foundation. This program was designed to specifically teach about and put into practice collaboration and team science skills. We had a social scientist who is an expert in the practice and science of team science that led training as part of the program. As a team, we explored a large diverse dataset, drafted, and submitted a manuscript. This fellowship, with its diverse and interdisciplinary lake expedition team, enabled me to develop skills such as authorship, communicating with different audiences, and learning the foundations of what makes a good team. Diversity is valuable, specifically when working on a project, due to the array of perspectives it brings. Different viewpoints allow honing the skill of finding common ground—a challenging yet

Fig. 3 Zoom meeting of a Lake Expedition 2020 meeting (Photo courtesy of Cary Institute of Ecosystem Studies)

crucial aspect, especially as an early career scientist. Through the mentorship of Dr. Paul Hanson (UW-Madison, Center for Limnology) and Dr. Kathleen Weathers (Cary Institute of Ecosystem Studies), we were able to do team science.

Not many graduate students have the opportunity to take a step back from their dissertation and immerse themselves in a completely different discipline. A Ph.D. trains you to become an expert in one particular field; however, there are many skills to be learned through collaborative projects. The research project that we worked on focused on using knowledge-guided machine learning to evaluate the surface area change of more than 100,000 lakes and reservoirs spanning 30 years of data. We engaged computer scientists to learn and use new skills in machine learning. When I was selected to be part of Lake Expedition, I was not expecting my whole perspective on science to change. Being part of a project that is different from your Ph.D. with a diverse team enriches you and your science by offering different perspectives, worldviews, and approaches that can influence or strengthen your own.

Through my Ph.D. journey, I learned how to communicate my science to diverse audiences, from the Board of Directors to first-year undergraduate labs to leaders in limnology. Working with teams where the work is distributed equally and where we help

each other while identifying my own strengths and weaknesses has been very valuable and vital for my professional development. I believe that the exposure I have received has better prepared me for the future, and encourage early career scientists to engage in collaborative research.

Publications

Meyer MF, ...Chapina RJ, ... Weathers KC. 2021. Virtual growing pains: Initial lessons learned from organizing virtual workshops, summits, conferences, and networking events during a global pandemic. *Limnology & Oceanography Bulletin*. 30: 1-11.

Stockwell JD, O'Malley BP, Hansson S, Chapina RJ, Rudstam LG, Weidel BC. 2020. Benthic habitat is an integral part of freshwater *Mysis* ecology. *Freshwater Biology*. 65: 1997-2009.

Chapina, R.J., C. Rowe, R. Woodland. 2020. Metabolic rates of *Neomysis americana* (Smith, 1873) (Mysida: Mysidae) from a temperate estuary vary in response to summer temperature and salinity conditions. *Journal of Crustacean Biology*. 40: 450-454.

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10324445>